

ALLERGIC RHINITIS IN CHILDREN

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Allergic rhinitis, according to modern data, affects up to a quarter of the population of developed countries. The disease affects not only the nasal mucosa, but also affects the receptors and mediators of inflammation in the bone marrow. A significant decrease in the quality of life of patients against the background of exacerbation of allergic rhinitis makes us look for new approaches to both the treatment of attacks and their prevention. Correction, including surgical, of concomitant pathology of the nasal cavity and paranasal sinuses significantly improves the quality of life of patients with allergic rhinitis. For a long time, surgical treatment of concomitant pathology of the nasal cavity in children was extremely limited due to the risk of damage to the growth zones and, as a consequence, a high probability of recurrence of deformation of the structures of the nose and paranasal sinuses. With the development of endoscopic methods of surgical treatment of the nasal cavity and paranasal sinuses, operations with minimal invasiveness and, as a consequence, safe at any age were introduced into practice. Surgical intervention on the structures of the lymphoid pharyngeal ring in children with allergic rhinitis is causing heated debate in the pediatric community to date. The article considers modern approaches to the diagnosis and treatment of allergic rhinitis in children. Topical problems of conservative and surgical treatment are discussed. Special attention is paid to the safety of various treatment regimens. The discussed practical issues of tactics of treatment of allergic rhinitis are relevant for both pediatric allergists and ENT pediatricians.

LITERATURES

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